

Implementation of Papua Special Region Autonomy in Relation to Defense Economy

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ABSTRACT : *Special Autonomy for Papua is the government's effort to solve Papua's problems by giving special authority to manage the Papua region so that the government can regulate all regional interests and meet the needs of the community. However, it is felt that the Special Autonomy policy has not had a sufficient impact on the community. The Papuan government needs to choose a strategy so that Special Autonomy for Papua can improve the welfare of the Papuan people. The purpose of this study is to analyze the strategies that the Papuan government can take in optimizing the Special Autonomy of its region. The analytical method used is to identify IFAS and EFAS with a SWOT analysis. The results of the study indicate that the Papuan Government can use the Turn Around strategy to optimize the authority of Special Autonomy to improve the welfare of the community and carry out monitoring efforts in determining policies and budget use.*

KEYWORDS –*Special Autonomy, Papua, Government Policy, SWOT, Defense Economy*

I. INTRODUCTION

Efforts made by the Government of Indonesia to improve the living standards of the people of Papua and West Papua are by establishing Papua and West Papua as Special Autonomous Regions or often referred to as Otsus. Otsus is a special power given to a "particular" region to regulate and manage the interests of the community through the rights and aspirations of its people according to that region's initiative. This authority is given so that 'certain' regions can organize regions and parts of the region to be better in certain fields following regional aspirations and be able to reduce inequality that can trigger turmoil in the community. [1].

There are several reasons behind the government's implementation of special autonomy in Papua. The decision to unify Papua as part of the United Republic of Indonesia is one of the goals of the United Republic of Indonesia. But in reality, Papua has a variety of government and development policies, including low utility, disparity in education and resource levels, human resources between migrants and locals, lack of infrastructure and connectivity, and bloody conflicts that often occur, still cause problems. turmoil in Papua. Even so, the state wants to solve various problems so that the government and the regions can progress. Therefore, in 1999 and 2000, MPRRI identified the need to grant special autonomy to Irian Jaya (the name Papua at the time). This is a positive first step in building public trust in the government as it works to solve Papua's problems.

The original draft of special autonomy stated that if Papua was granted special autonomy, the revenues would have to be shared with the central government, and 20% of Papua itself would be 80%. There is still disagreement on this issue. However, this is to help balance the state budget of the Republic of Indonesia. This is one of the provisions for the implementation of special autonomy in Papua. Unfortunately, the implementation of Papua's special autonomy is close to unilateral action by the central government. To correct the shortcomings of this special autonomy policy, the government has made several revisions to the policy.

II. REASERCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative method involving a literature review using various articles on Papua's Special Autonomy (Otsus) related to the defense economy. This study also uses some financial data published by local governments and the ministry of finance and in writing this scientific paper also uses news that is presented from trusted news websites regarding events or conditions in Papua related to the economy. The data that has been obtained were analyzed using the SWOT method. SWOT analysis is used to identify internal and external factors that affect Otsus Papua so that it can be concluded what strategies can be used by the Regional Government of Papua in responding to the Otsus policy given by the Central Government optimally.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To be able to discuss the success of a government, a lot of literature has explored this. According to Hartzell (1999) one of the references to the success of the government is being able to reduce conflict and provide stability in a minority area through the government itself effectively and at the same time being able to maintain the territorial integrity of the country itself [2]. Although apart from this, conflict resolution, development promotion, and democracy can be a sign of the success of the government itself. The granting of Otsus to Papua, both in the province of West Papua and Papua itself, provides opportunities and challenges in achieving success in terms of economic prosperity, health, conflict, and separatism..

Analysis of the Strengths and Weaknesses of Papua's Special Autonomy

As a region that has special autonomy status and is ratified by law, the Papuan government in carrying out government activities in its territory has several special rights to be managed independently. The government can manage various economic activities in accordance with local wisdom in the region. To support this, the government provides the opportunity for indigenous Papuans to express the aspirations of their citizens through the Papuan People's Council (MRP). The MRP exists as a form of Papuan representation in government to best serve the Papuan people and also has a specific agenda related to respect for customs and culture, and protection of the rights of indigenous Papuans based on women's empowerment. has the authority to, strengthen religious harmony. Through this, the MRP is expected to be able to enforce the customary laws of life in the community and their legitimacy is recognized as formal law [3]. It is also hoped that the existence of cultural practices of the Papuan people will be recognized by special symbols, naming of institutions and naming of special rules that represent the existence of Papua. The existence of this MRP is not found in other areas. The existence of the MRP itself can be said to be a legislature in the Papuan government bureaucracy. The authority borne by the MRP is large, therefore the MRP determines concrete steps for the specificity of the Papuan government.

From the budget side, the Government has again extended special autonomy (Otsus) for the provinces of Papua and West Papua from 2022 to 2041. This is as regulated in Law (UU) Number 2 of 2021 concerning the Second Amendment to Law Number 21 of 2001 concerning Special Autonomy for Papua Province which was promulgated on July 19, 2021. Regarding local income, Papua has special regulations. Papua is characterized by a profit-sharing fund level of 70% for natural resources in the oil extraction sector and 70% for natural gas extraction. This percentage is higher than the percentages regulated in other regions where the profit share for oil exploration in the region is 15.5% and natural gas is 30.05%. In addition, there is a "special revenue" for the implementation of special autonomy, the amount of which is equal to 2% of the National General Allocation Fund (DAU) cap. Since 2017 the receipt of special allocations in the Papua and West Papua regions has tended to increase, but due to the Covid-19 Pandemic, allocation receipts have decreased in 2020 and 2021 as shown in table 1. In 2021 the government again allocates a budget of Rp. 8.5 trillion for Papua and West Papua special autonomy in the 2022 State Budget Draft (RAPBN). This fund is 12.6% higher, similar to the 2021 APBN prospect. Rp. 7.6 trillion. The amount of the Special Autonomy Fund also increased to 2.25% of the General Allocation Fund (DAU) limit [4].

However, Papua's special autonomy cannot be explained as a kind of collective bargaining agreement, but as an achievement of the central government to reduce conflicts occurring in Papua. If Aceh's special autonomy is a follow-up to dispute resolution, Papua's special autonomy is an attempt to resolve disputes. As a

result, there are still many Papuans who do not share a common understanding of the existence of special autonomy among the parties to the conflict. For the central government, special autonomy is a concrete effort to resolve conflicts, and for some communities in Papua, special autonomy is the central government's attempt to stop their resistance. In addition, the background of the establishment of the Special Autonomy Law for Papua aims to resolve the root causes of conflict and aspirations of the Papuan people. Although the law already requires the participation of the Papuan people in managing their area, it is felt that Otsus Papua is only a prescriptive tool to solve the root causes of problems in the form of inequality, equal opportunity, protection of basic rights, and human rights [3]. This situation is exacerbated by the Regional Government which is still behaving corruptly, as evidenced by the findings of the financial audit by the BPK which is one of the criteria that the regional government has not carried out its responsibilities in using the budget and authority as a region that has Special Autonomy [5].

Analysis of Opportunities and Challenges of Special Autonomy for Papua

The Special Autonomy Fund is actually a fund given by the government to the provinces of Papua and West Papua to be able to support the resolution of education, health and economic problems in the region. These funds are exclusively given by the central government to local governments so that the standard of living of the Papuan people improves and is on par with other regions in the province. Local governments are expected to be able to manage and use these funds to make policies, programs or activities that directly impact the three main problems. The Provincial Government can work together with district and city governments to be able to carry out programs or activities that have been prepared in order to generate real benefits for the needs, initiatives and expectations of the Papuan people. Previously, the amount of the Special Autonomy Fund was the upper limit of two percent of the DAU. The addition of the Special Autonomy Fund allocation was due to the need for large development costs in Papua and West Papua due to high geographical difficulties. The funds will then be used for two policy developments. First, for the development and maintenance of facilities and infrastructure for the provision of public services, improving the welfare of indigenous Papuans (OAP), and strengthening traditional institutions and activities that are local priorities. Second, the allocation for education and health improvement is at least thirty and twenty percent, respectively, as well as for increasing community financial empowerment.

Local governments can keep the indigenous Papuans alive in all forms of local wisdom. Indonesia recognizes that every local culture and language is part of the Archipelago Insight. The government needs to provide support to indigenous people to continue to be able to preserve the local wisdom. First, providing space and opportunity for indigenous Papuans to be able to give more open opinions on important opportunities such as village development, regional infrastructure, and even related economic growth in the Papua region. A government that listens to the needs of the community will be able to provide a bond that indigenous Papuans are not abandoned or isolated. Second, Indonesian is the unified language of the local language. Each tribe generally has its traditional language. The government can provide teaching staff to continue to strengthen the Indonesian language as a unified language without neglecting the customary language in every region in Papua. This is important because the founders of the Indonesian nation realized that, when Indonesians did not have a unified language, this nation could be divided.

The government continues to encourage Papua to be able to continue to develop in terms of economy, welfare, and politics so that the quality of life of the Papuan people will be better. One of the policies carried out is to provide equal distribution of regional development with regional expansion. With the revision of the Special Autonomy Law [6], the Papua region can be divided into regions so that the government can be present to reach areas where regional development is still lagging. However, this policy may be rejected by a group of people who think this expansion will oppress residents [7]. The government must be ready to provide arguments if there are differences of opinion regarding the expansion of the region. In addition, every time there is an expansion of the region, of course, there will be the addition of the local regional police officers and the TNI. The central government and local governments can coordinate to determine defense and security spatial policies. The regional expansion is expected to be able to build defense and security support facilities in the expanded area so that the spatial structure of defense and security forces will be more spread out in new, smaller areas. It

can also break up the OPM separatist movement that occurs in the region by employing rebellion and armed violence. The development of defense and security forces will also support the regional development process that has been facing these threats. That way, the acceleration of development in the Papua region will be realized simultaneously.

From the institutional side in Papua, agencies that are directly related to improving people's welfare such as educational institutions, health regulatory institutions, economic regulatory institutions, and infrastructure regulatory institutions have not shown good, responsive, and accountable performance on the reference performance indicators of each related institution [8]. For this reason, special attention is needed from high leaders, the community, and supervisory institutions to increase the capacity of human resources towards institutions, authorities, and financial policies related to education, health, economy, and infrastructure. [2].

Table1. SWOT analysis of Papua Special Autonomy

STRENGTHS
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have the freedom to manage, develop and run their local government independently. 2. Obtaining a budget as an Otsus area. 3. Having the MRP as a cultural representation of the Papuan people and the existence of the use of the Papuan symbol.
WEAKNESSES
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Otsus Papua was formed not as a result of a mutual agreement but to reduce the conflict that occurred. 2. The presence of the Papuan people to have representatives in the government does not solve the aspirations of the people. 3. Lack of Supervision of corrupt local governments who abuse the budget and authority given to the Special Autonomy Region.
OPPORTUNITIES
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increasing Papuan people's life expectancy, education, and standard of living through government budget support. 2. Equitable regional development. 3. Additional Defense and Security Forces through regional expansion.
THREATS
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The budget implementing agency related to improving the welfare of the community is not optimal. 2. Refusal to expand territory 3. Separatism.

Based on the table1, it can be seen what the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats faced by the Papua special autonomy policy.

These results are analyzed in table2 using an internal factor score (IFAS) with a strength factor of 1.3 and a weakness factor score of 1.45.

Table2 IFAS Results

	Internal Factor Strategy	Weight	Rating	Score
Strengths				
1.	Have the freedom to manage, develop and run their local government independently.	0,3	3	0,9
2.	Obtaining a budget as an Otsus area.	0,1	3	0,3
3.	Having the MRP as a cultural representation of the Papuan people and the existence of the use of the Papuan symbol.	0,1	1	0,1

	Sub Total	0,5		1,3
Weakness				
1.	Otsus Papua was formed not as a result of a mutual agreement but to reduce the conflict that occurred.	0,3	3	0,9
2.	The presence of the Papuan people to have representatives in the government does not solve the aspirations of the people.	0,05	2	0,1
3.	Lack of Supervision of corrupt local governments who abuse the budget and authority given to the Special Autonomy Region.	0,15	3	0,45
	Sub Total	0,5		1,45
	Total	1		2,75

Like the IFAS analysis, the external strategy factor (EFAS) is also identified with the results of the EFAS analysis showing that the opportunity factor has a score of 1.675 while the threat factor has a score of 1.6. as the table below is as follows:

Table 3 EFAS Results

	External Factor Strategy	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunities				
1.	Increasing Papuan people's life expectancy, education, and standard of living through government budget support.	0,175	4	0,7
2.	Equitable regional development.	0,185	3	0,555
3.	Additional Defense and Security Forces through regional expansion.	0,14	3	0,42
	Sub Total	0,5		1,675
Threats				
1.	The budget implementing agency related to improving the welfare of the community is not optimal.	0,2	4	0,8
2.	Refusal to expand territory	0,05	1	0,05
3.	Separatism.	0,25	3	0,75
	Sub Total	0,5		1,6
	Total	1		3,275

Based on table 2 and table 3, it can be detailed the score of each factor Strength: 1.3 Weakness: 1.45 Opportunity: 1.675 and Threat: 1.6. So that the strength score is the result that the weakness score is greater than the strengths of (-) 0.15 and the opportunity score is greater than the threat of (+) 0.075.

Based on the results of the identification of these factors, it can be depicted in the Cartesian diagram that the strategy that can be used is Turn-Around.

Figure 1 : Cartesian Diagram of Otsus Papua

Source: Data processed by the author from the results of the analysis of IFAS and EFAS Otsus Papua

From figure 1 it can be seen that the implementation of Otsus Papua is in a Turn-Around position by review the purpose of Otsus to be able to improve the quality of life of the Papuan people as well as evaluating the performance achievements of the policy on the implementation of Otsus Papua.

The following describes the combination of policies on internal and external factors that can be taken about the Otsus Papua policy.

Strength-Opportunity Strategy (Growth Strategy)

This strategy uses all the opportunities that are available with the enactment of Papua as an Otsus region with the power of having a special policy given to the implementation of Otsus. The power-opportunity strategy of Otsus Papua is for the government to work closely with the MRP to obtain detailed community needs so that the local government's budget policy is effective. Acceleration of equity through expansion can be done by taking into account that the new areas will later receive better services. The government is more able to reach the area to carry out development both in terms of the economy as well as space for defense and security.

Strength-Threat Strategy (Diversification Strategy)

This strategy uses all the strengths of the Otsus policy to overcome the threat by continuing to equalize the development of the quality of life of the local community where conflicts and resistance to separatist movements often occur. In addition, the Papuan government continues to communicate with the MRP and indigenous peoples to participate in guarding and supervising government activities so that they continue to run according to community expectations.

Weakness-Opportunity Strategy (Turn-Around Strategy)

This strategy takes advantage of the opportunities possessed by the Otsus policy to deal with the government's internal weaknesses, namely by evaluating the use of the budget for policies related to efforts to increase the life expectancy of the Papuan people, education and living standards in each region, especially remote and remote areas. The government can expand the territory by taking into account the acceleration of equitable distribution of regional development. The regional government together with the center also work together to continue to monitor the performance and use of the budget from the Office which is directly related to efforts to increase the life expectancy of the Papuan people. The status as a special autonomous region must be utilized as best as possible by the regional government so that the Papuan people can feel the presence of the government from all aspects of life.

Weakness-Threat Strategy (Defensive Strategy)

The Weakness-Threat Strategy seeks to minimize the impact of the weak Otsus Papua as well as external threats that hinder the improvement of the quality of life of the Papuan people by focusing on improving the internal government of the local government by minimizing the existence of corruptive actions from the government officials themselves. The government cooperates with the MRP and local communities to create activities that can improve people's lives as well as the actualization of the existence of Otsus Papua as a form of the government effort to be present for the community. In addition, the opportunity for regional expansion policies must be well communicated with the community so that there are no misunderstandings in the decision-making process. This communication is needed so that no turmoil that can provide an opportunity for the separatist movement to call for the independence of Papua from Indonesia.

IV. CONCLUSION

This article concludes that Otsus Papua uses the Turn Around Strategy to take advantage of every opportunity for the privilege of this special autonomy to minimize the weaknesses that cause the goals and expectations of the granting of special autonomy to Papua not to be achieved. It must be admitted that the Papuan local government has not been optimal in managing the budget so supervision is needed so that the implementation of public policies, especially those related to improving living standards, education, and living standards has not been achieved. The findings of the BPK examination still show the existence of corrupt behavior by local governments. Institutional improvements are needed so that the special autonomy status for Papua can be felt the benefits the Papuan people. Expansion efforts in the context of equitable development, economy, and spatial security and defense can be carried out to improve the living standards of the Papuan people and prevent inequality between regions from getting higher.

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